

RESEARCH ON FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF COUGH SYRUP (RESPIRATORY TRACT INFECTION) BY USING TINOSPORIDE CORDIFOLIA EXTRACT.

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ABSTRACT:

Background:-*Tinospora cordifolia* (Wild.) Miers, commonly known as Guduchi or Giloy, is a highly esteemed medicinal plant in traditional systems such as Ayurveda, Unani, and Siddha. Cough is a widespread respiratory condition affecting people of all age groups, necessitating effective and safe treatment options. Cough can be classified as dry (non-productive) or wet (productive, with mucus). Increasing incidence of cough due to pollution and allergies highlights the need for natural remedies like Giloy-based formulations.

Method: The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of an herbal cough syrup using aqueous and hydroalcoholic extracts of *Tinospora cordifolia* stem. The syrup was prepared using suitable excipients including sweeteners, preservatives, and flavoring agents to enhance palatability and stability. The formulated syrup was evaluated for key physicochemical parameters such as pH, viscosity, and density using standard protocols.

Result: The formulated syrup exhibited acceptable physicochemical characteristics, including stable pH, appropriate viscosity, and favorable density. The combination of *Tinospora cordifolia* extracts and selected excipients resulted in a palatable and stable herbal cough formulation.

Conclusion: The study concludes that cough syrup formulated using *Tinospora cordifolia* stem extract provides a natural, safe, and effective alternative to conventional synthetic cough formulations. It is especially beneficial for managing cough associated with pollution and allergies, with minimal side effects.

KEYWORDS:- Gulvel , Cough , Bronchodilator , Expectorant , Herbal , Extraction , Anti-inflammatory , Evaluation.

INTRODUCTION- Another name for *Tinospora cordifolia* is Giloy, Guduchi. One of the most important herbs used in indigenous medicine is *Tinospora Cordifolia*^[1]. From Kumaon to Assam in the north, and to West Bengal, Bihar, the Decan Kankan, Karnataka, and Kerala in the south, it can be found in tropical parts of India that reach elevations of up to 1200 meters. Furthermore, North Africa, South Africa, Bangladesh, Malaysia, Myanmar, and Vietnam are home to Giloy species^[2]. *Tinospora cordifolia*, a member of the Menispermaceae family, is generally known as "Guduchi" in Sanskrit. Alkaloids, steroids, diterpenoids, lactones, aliphatic compounds, and glycosides are among the many active ingredients that have been extracted from the plant's various parts, including the root, stem, and entire plant. According to estimates from the World Health Organization (WHO), up to 80% of people still primarily use traditional medications made from medicinal plants. Plants have been utilized as natural remedies since the dawn of human civilization. The creation of novel medications from traditional medicinal plants has recently attracted the attention of scientists^[3]. India offers a solid foundation for the use of several plants in general healthcare and common diseases due to its enormous biodiversity and extensive understanding of historic traditional medical systems like Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani. Because of its high nutritional content, the stem of giloy is said to be quite beneficial^[4]. There are several chemical components in *Tinospora Cordifolia* that may affect the body. While some of these chemicals have anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities, others may increase the activity of the immune system and prevent respiratory tract infections. A number of substances

may be effective against cancer cells in test animals. Most of the study has been done on animals or in test tubes. There are several components of the Giloy plant that can be used, but the stem is the most useful and beneficial^[5]. There are several chemical components in *Tinospora Cordifolia* that may affect the body. While some of these chemicals have anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities, others may increase the activity of the immune system and prevent respiratory tract infections. A number of substances may be effective against cancer cells in test animals. Most of the study has been done on animals or in test tubes. There are several components of the Giloy plant that can be used, but the stem is the most useful and beneficial^[6]. Many people believe that herbal remedies are the best way to treat coughs, and they have a big impact on the healthcare industry. Asthma, TB, cough, pneumonia, renal disease, cancer, diabetes, allergies, lung cancer, and viral infections are just a few of the minor to serious illnesses that these natural formulations are used to treat. Around 80% of people worldwide, according to WHO estimates, get their primary medical treatment from herbal remedies. Traditional medicine has always included medicinal herbs, particularly in Asian nations^[7]. Instead than treating life-threatening illnesses, their major purpose is to maintain health and manage chronic ailments. Synthetic medications, on the other hand, frequently have a number of negative effects, including sleepiness, nausea, vomiting, allergies, respiratory infections, changes in appetite, irritability, sedation, and, in certain situations, addiction or organ damage from overuse. Herbal remedies have garnered more attention in recent years because of their little or non-existent adverse effects both during and after therapy^[8]. **Chemical constituent Alkaloid** – *Berberine, Palmatine, Tetrahydropalmatine Glycoside(diterpenoid)* – *Tinosporaside, cordifoliside* **Flavonoids** – *Quercetin, kaempferol* **Other constituent-** *Tinosporin, Cordifolin*. Gulvel's stem extract is frequently mixed with natural components including mentha, turmeric, ginger, carom seed, glycerine, and honey to create cough syrups. These ingredients work well to treat coughs and respiratory conditions because of their well-known anti-inflammatory, antitussive (cough-relieving), expectorant (phlegm-loosening), immunomodulatory, and antioxidant qualities. . In these compositions, honey is used as the basis and sweetener. According to studies, these herbal cough syrups work well for treating long-term illnesses like respiratory infections, fevers, colds, and coughs^[9].

Fig.No-1 Gulvel Stem

Objective:-

- To develop a stable herbal syrup using *Tinosporide cordifolia* extract.
- Optimize the combination of natural ingredient to enhance therapeutic benefit.
- Evaluate antimicrobial, Anti-inflammatory activity against respiratory pathogens.
- Determine viscosity for appropriate consistency.
- Measure the PH level to ensure stability.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

1. Collection of information about the herbal plant.
2. Selection of herbal plant.
3. Authentication of herbal plant.
4. Extraction of bio-active compound.
5. Identification of bio active compound by using different chromatography.
6. Selection of herbal excipient .

7. Excipients convert into powder.
8. Preparation of solution.
9. Final syrup preparation.
10. Evaluation test.
11. Conclusion.
12. Report writing.
13. Presentation of data.

MATERIAL-

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Quantity	Role of Ingredient
1.	Gulvel stem extract	35ml	Bronchodilator & Immunomodulator
2.	Mentha	12ml	Anti-inflammatory
3.	Turmeric	6ml	Antibacterial
4.	Ginger	6ml	Antitussive
5.	Carom	6ml	Expectorant
6.	Honey	22ml	Base viscosity
7.	Jaggery	10ml	Sweetening agent
8.	Sodium benzoate	2ml	Preservative
9.	Vanilla	q.s.	Flavouring agent

Table No.1-Material

METHOD-

Preparation of gulvel stem powder

1. Collection of fresh gulvel stem from healthy plant.
2. Wash the stem thoroughly with distilled water to remove out dust particle
3. Cut the stem and into small particles (1-2 inch) using the cutter
4. Dry properly by using sun drying for 7-8 days and remove out moisture.
5. Grind the stem by using grinder and convert into the Powder. And after that powder used mortar pestle.
6. In final step, powder pass from the sieve (Mesh size 10) to get a fine powder and uniform size.

Extraction Process:-

1. Collect the gulvel fine powder.
2. Take a water and add in Powder
3. Then mix properly.
4. Gulvel solution packed and stored for 24-48 hrs.
5. And after extraction process filtration the mixture and collect the filtrate.

Identification test -**Fig.No-2 Identification test**

Identification Test For Glycoside			
Sr.no	Test	Observation	Inference
1	Killer killani test	Reddish brown colour.	Present.
2	Leagl test	Slightly reddish brown colour.	Present.
3	Foam test	Formation of foam.	Slightly present
4	Borntrager test	Reddish brown or pinkish colour.	Present.

Table No.2- Identification Test

In glycoside(diterpenoid), present the two main bio component such as tinosporaside and cordifoliside which have synergetic effect it reducing the inflammation and use for the cough treatment but tinosporaside shows the more effect for bronchodilator and loose the phlegm .In *Tinospora cordifolia* (Glycoside diterpenoid) present tinosporaside and cordifoliside has been use to seperate to component by using liquid liquid extraction tinosporaside are purely soluble in water because highly pure Glycoside and cordifoliside slightly soluble in water (soluble in organic solvent) because furonoditerpenoid glycoside with lower polarity

Separation Process:-

- Take a seprating funnel.
- Add a solution in seprating funnel with water and Chloroform.
- Stir properly and stable for 15 Minute.
- And observe formation of two layer aqueous phase(lower layer) and organic phase(upper layer).
- In last step, collect the lower layer(aqueous phase because in aqueous phase present tinosporaside bio-active compound)

Fig.No-3 Separation Process

Detection of compound:-

By using thin layer chromatography. TLC is a simple, quick and effective method for separating and analysing small amount of compound in mixture.

1. Preparation of TLC plate
2. Sample of Application
3. Development Of Plate
4. Visualization
5. Analysis of Result

Thin layer chromatography	Observation			
	Solute front	Solvent front	Rf Value	Spot colour
	2.5	8.3	0.30	Bluish purple

Table No.3- Observation

Preparation of Excipient Extraction :-

1. Take 10gm of mentha leaves powder with 100 ml of distilled water and heat slowly For 2-3 minute and filtered the extract.
2. Take 10 gm of turmeric powder with 100 ml of distilled water and heat slowly For 2-3 minute and filtered the extract.
3. Take 10 gm of Carom seeds powder with 100 ml of distilled water and heat slowly For 2-3 minute and filtered the extract.
4. Take 10 gm of Ginger powder with 100 ml of distilled water and heat slowly For 2-3 minute and filtered the extract.
5. Take a 5g of jagary with some amount of water & heat slowly & filter.
6. Filter was taken to prepare final syrup.

Fig.No-4 Excipient Extraction

Final Syrup preparation:-

1. Weight and measuring all ingredients accurately.
2. Mix all ingredients and stir well properly.
3. Adding honey to mix and stir.
4. Add some amount of Jaggery and stir.
5. And then add the Sodium benzoate and Vanilla.
6. All ingredients properly mixed and stir and then heating.
7. In last step cool the mixture and filtered.
8. After the prepared final syrup transferred into amberd colour bottle and neat label, stored in cool and dry place.

Fig.No-5 Final Syrup

Evaluation parameter:-**A. Physicochemical test:-**

- **Colour Examination:** - A 5 ml sample of the final syrup was placed in watch glasses and observed under white tube light against a white background. Its colour was assessed visually with the naked eye.
- **Odour Examination:** - 2ml of final syrup sample were each smell. 2 min was the time interval between scents in order to counteract the effect of the preceding scent.
- **Taste Examination:** - A pinch of final syrup was taken and examined for its taste on taste buds of the tongue.

B. PH Determination :- Take a pH strip and 10ml of final syrup in a beaker and dip pH strip in syrup solution and observe and compare with standard pH paper.

C. Specific gravity :-

- Clean and dry the specific gravity bottle along with its stopper
- Weigh the empty bottle with stopper (w_1).
- Fill with distilled water and weigh (w_2). (maintained 27 ± 1 °C)
- And remove water & fill with sample and weigh. (w_3).

D. Viscosity Determination :- Viscosity of syrup can be determined by using Ostwald viscometer. First clean the Ostwald viscometer thoroughly with acetone. Place the viscometer in vertical position on a stand now fill the water up to mark "G" in dry viscometer. Note the time required for water to flow from mark A to mark B. For at least three times, repeat the filling process and note the time to obtain accurate readings. Now rinse the viscometer and fill it with test liquid (syrup) till mark A, find out the time required for liquid to flow to mark B. The density can be determined by using specific gravity bottle.

Observation and Calculation:-

- **Determination of specific gravity of liquid :**

Observation-

1. Weight of empty specific gravity bottle (w_1) = 13.58 gm.
2. Weight of specific gravity bottle + Distilled water (w_2) = 20.20gm.
3. Weight of specific gravity + liquid (syrup solution) (w_3) = 20.13 gm.

Calculation :-

1. Mass of the liquid (syrup solution) = $W_3 - W_1 = 20.13 - 13.58 = 6.55$ gm.
2. Mass of the distilled water = $W_2 - W_1 = 20.20 - 13.58 = 6.62$ gm.
3. Specific gravity of liquid (syrup solution) = Mass of liquid (syrup solution) / Mass of equal volume of water. **SG = 6.55/6.62 = 0.989**

- **Determination of Density of liquid :-**

1. Density of water at room temperature (p_1) = 0.997g/ml (Standard value)
2. Specific gravity of syrup solution = 0.989
3. Specific gravity of liquid = Density of liquid (Syrup Solution) / Density of Distilled water.
4. Density of liquid (Syrup Solution) (p_2) = specific gravity of liquid (syrup solution) x Density of Distilled water.

$$(p_2) = 0.989 \times 0.997 \quad (p_2) = 0.98603 \text{ g/ml}$$

5. Density of liquid sample (syrup solution) = **0.98603 g/ml**

- **Determination of viscosity of liquid :-**

1. Viscosity of liquid (n_2) = $P_2 t_2 / P_1 t_1 \times n_1$
2. P_1 = Density of water (g/ml)
3. P_2 = Density of test sample (syrup solution)
4. N_1 = Viscosity of water (cp)
5. N_2 = Viscosity of test sample (syrup solution)
6. T_1 = Mean time of flow of flow of water from A to B
7. T_2 = Mean time of flow of test (sample syrup)
8. Viscosity of water at room temp $n_1 = 0.997$ cp ($0.98603 \times 95.3 / 0.997 \times 25.14$) x 0.997
9. Viscosity of syrup solution at room temp is = **3.73 cp**

RESULTS:

Sr.No	Parameter	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃
1.	Physicochemical Parameter			
	a) Colour	Brownish colour	Brownish colour	Brownish colour
	b) Odour	Aromatic	Aromatic	Aromatic
	c) Taste	Sweet	Sweet	Sweet

2.	PH Determination	Acidic	Acidic	Acidic
3.	Specific gravity	0.973	0.443	0.989
4.	Density	0.97008 g/ml	0.441679 g/ml	0.98603
5.	Viscosity	3.71 cp	2.05 cp	3.73 cp

DISCUSSION :- In the present study, three batches of syrup (**F1, F2, and F3**) were formulated and evaluated using standard parameters such as appearance, pH, viscosity, and stability. All the batches were prepared successfully, and the evaluation parameters were properly applied. Among them, batch F3 was found to be the best in terms of overall quality and performance. It showed desirable physical characteristics, acceptable pH, appropriate viscosity, and density. Therefore, **Batch F3** can be considered the most optimized and suitable formulation for further development.

CONCLUSION: The present study successfully formulates and evaluated Gulvel Cough (respiratory infection) Syrup, leveraging the therapeutic potential of *Tinospora cordifolia* (tinosporaside) as a natural bioactive agent. The results of phytochemical, pharmacological, and toxicological assessments underscore the syrup's efficacy in managing cough, bronchial irritation, and respiratory inflammation through its well-documented antitussive, mucolytic, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory properties. The various scientific studies that have been conducted on *T.cordifolia* state that it is effective against cough. Phytochemical profiling confirmed the presence of bioactive constituent's diterpenoid glycosides, which collectively contribute to its therapeutic action by modulating phlegm loosing, immune response, reducing oxidative stress, and suppressing inflammatory cytokines.

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